

Sustainability of Public Colleges Retaining Lecturers through Innovative and Proactive Leadership

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Abstract

Lecturers' retention is a challenging issue in public colleges since their turnover rate is sensitive, therefore, innovative and proactive leadership is key element to address the very trend by the means of different kinds of attractive provisions to empower lecturers' to check turnover rate.

This study aims at exploring the fundamental reasons behind lecturers' turnover from public colleges and analyzes the existing human resource provision of public colleges to motivate their professional development associating the commitment of existing college regulation, practices, complimentarily with university as well.

Empirical research was applied. Public colleges of Nepal were population and public colleges of Madhesh were sample. Strata were made to select sample colleges and lecturers. Data was collected through in depth interview to collect lecturers' perception and existing human resource (HR) policy provisions were studied using historical study through library study. Abraham Maslow's 'Need Hierarchy Theory' was linked with lecturers 'perception for analysis of the issue of the study.

The findings reveal that prevailing provisions are inadequate to motivate lecturers' in terms of their financial security, career path, professional development and individual growth in changing scenario. Similarly the policy level management practices lack farsighted perspectives in globally dynamic HR dimensions and lacks the authentic analysis of external HR environment. Similarly grievance handling practices is weak that is leading venerable institutional relation provoking internal conflicts [Industrial Relation].

Top level management of the public colleges need to restructure the management practices substituting the traditional one with contingent approach that can yield fruitful results being adjusted with particular situation. HR policies must be proactive to address the lecturers' need and aspirations for sustainability of public colleges though innovative leadership instead of traditional and reactive.

Keywords: Public colleges, lecturers' retention, prospective and innovative leadership, sustainability, institutional relation.